

Exploring Effective Strategies for Teaching Practical Procedures in Text and Image Editing

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Abstract

In the era of the knowledge economy, the integration of information technology into several sectors has caused a significant shift in the editing and publishing industry. This study investigates efficient instructional methods for manipulating text and images, with a particular focus on utilizing Adobe InDesign (ID) software. The report highlights the shift from traditional manual editing methods to digital processes, emphasizing the importance of digital intelligence skills in modern publishing. The study seeks to examine several facets of editing in Adobe InDesign, encompassing master page editing, text manipulation, image modification, vector graphics manipulation, color adjustment, object manipulation, line modification, table manipulation, layout modification, and packaging techniques. The study employs a conceptual analytic framework to examine these issues, providing comprehensive guidance for both inexperienced and experienced designers. The findings indicate that effective use of ID requires an understanding of both the theoretical and practical aspects of graphic design. Users can determine job priorities by categorizing important strategies into three levels of importance: necessary, recommended, and optional. The study also investigates the impact of visual aesthetics, the incorporation of text and images, and the significance of innovation in producing captivating and coherent designs. This study makes a significant contribution to the profession by providing structured methods and useful knowledge to improve text and image editing abilities. The statement underscores the need to strike a balance between visual appeal and functional clarity, ensuring that each visual element enhances the overall effectiveness of the publication in effectively expressing its message. The operational strategies described in this study are a valuable asset for maximizing productivity and achieving excellent results in graphic projects.

Keywords: editing, text, image, computer operation, practical teaching.

Introduction

In the knowledge economy era, using information in conjunction with learning, managing, storing, transmitting, and applying knowledge is an important cultural indicator. As a result, the development and application of various computer software have flourished, ushering in the information economy era. In this era, with the prevalence of computers and the integration of information into life, an unprecedented digital cultural trend has emerged. Integrating computers into various fields has become a structural development foundation, and digital intelligence capabilities and applications have become the mainstream of social development.

In terms of editing and publishing, computer typesetting and editing software have been continuously innovating. Professional editing and typesetting in printing plants have become widespread in personal desktop publishing (DTP). Consequently, the traditional magazine editing model has transformed into one centered on digital computer technology editing. Wang

Shouzhi (2000) believed that after 1990, the rapid development of computers and the successive emergence of editing software triggered a major revolution in publishing design. Regardless of layout, text, and image arrangement and processing techniques, they have replaced the traditional manual operation mode. Hong Ruwen (2000) also believed that since the 1990s, the typesetting and publishing functions of desktop computers had reached a mature stage, eliminating the need to seek editing and production from printing plants, as anyone could learn and utilize them. By 1993, computer software applications had replaced the traditional photographic typesetting method. Currently, the more familiar layout software includes QuarkXPress and PageMaker. Sun Binggang (2008) pointed out that after version 4.1, QuarkXPress no longer released Chinese versions. The update issues for PageMaker 7 and later versions have received attention. Therefore, these two updates have impacted users. Simultaneously, since version 2.0, InDesign has been able to integrate Chinese functionality and has been updating rapidly. In less than two years, the latest InDesign version, CS 5.5, will undergo an upgrade to CS 6.0. Thus, InDesign has gradually become an important application software for editing, layout, and publishing. Steven Heller and Teresa Fernandes (2006) believe that computers are the main design tools today, but computer technology cannot replace design talent. As a result, computers are irreplaceable in terms of human brain innovation and creativity.

This concept dictates that one must first draft a work into a blueprint, after which the computer can actualize the work in accordance with the blueprint. This is the relationship between human conception and computer application. Gao Junmao (1995) pointed out that the content of drafts and sketches includes text, illustrations, outlines, and tables. Drafts serve the primary purpose of reviewing the overall atmosphere, color, and composition of the work to ensure compliance with aesthetic principles, and then adding, deleting, and adjusting the content and proportions. Huang Dunyan (1991) proposed that we can analyze visual perception using a page's structural layout, which includes the positional planning of titles and illustrations within the page frame. Therefore, it is important to avoid clutter in the planning of illustrations and text on the page to ensure a clear and easy-to-understand layout that will pique readers' interest in the work. Incorporating artistic design is crucial to enhancing readers' perceptions. Thus, this study considers both the concept of magazine editing and the practical operation of the InDesign software, aiming to inspire beginners' thinking and application abilities.

This study aims to explore the following topics: 1. the concept of master page editing and ID operation strategies; 2. the concept of text editing and ID operation strategies; 3. the concept of image editing and ID operation strategies; 4. the concept of vector graphics editing and ID operation strategies; 5. the concept of color editing and ID strategies; 6. the concept of object editing and ID operation strategies; 7. The concept of line editing and ID operation strategies; 8. The concept of table editing and ID operation strategies; 9. The concept of layout editing and ID operation strategies; 10. The concept of illustration and text editing and ID operation strategies; 11. The concept of packaging and ID strategies. This study's research limitations focus on graphic design without discussing article solicitation or invitation. Additionally, the latest version of Adobe InDesign is CS5.5, which has the ability to create e-books, PDFs, and websites, but these functionalities are not within the scope of this research.

This study utilizes conceptual analysis, a type of informational analysis, to examine issues related to magazine graphic editing as well as strategies for executing graphic editing using computer application software. The relevant topics are as follows: master pages, text, images, vectors, colors, editing, lines, tables, layouts, illustrations and text, and packaging. Using Mr. Wang Xiu's list of 14 magazine categories for conceptual analysis, we employ a non-structural and non-systematic approach to scrutinize the text, images, and covers before combining and

elucidating the underlying concepts. The 14 categories are: business management, social humanities, leisure and entertainment, natural sciences, children and youth, science and technology, finance and investment, language education, consumer lifestyle, arts and literature, health and medicine, internet and communications, news and information, and fashion trends. For computer operations, we use Adobe InDesign CS 5.5 (also known as ID), which incorporates computer practice into the research process. This version lists the practical operation strategies for the 11 graphic editing topics mentioned earlier. We divide the operation strategies into three levels based on their importance: Level 1 (required), Level 2 (recommended), and Level 3 (optional). "Required" refers to necessary steps; "recommended" refers to optional steps that can improve operation and design; and "optional" refers to steps the designer can choose to perform or ignore. Computer operations primarily focus on the "File," "View," "Text," "Table," and "Layout" menus in the function list. For files, operations include creating new, opening existing, placing, saving, document setup, file information, and packaging. For layouts, the operations encompass the layout grid, pages, margins, and columns. Text operations include font size, writing direction, characters, paragraphs, insertion points, glyphs, character styles, paragraph styles, grid styles, composite fonts, keep options, text justification, and path text. For objects, operations include transforming, repeating transformations, stacking order, selecting, frame types, frame grid options, text frame options, anchoring objects, aligning, contents, effects, corner options, clipping paths, interactivity, paths, path manager, converting shapes, and display performance. For tables, operations include table options, cell options, inserting, deleting, selecting, and converting rows. For views, the operations include overprint preview, proof setup, proof colors, zooming in, zooming out, fitting page in window, fitting spread in window, actual size, entire pasteboard, rotating spread view, screen modes, display performance, structure, show/hide text threads, hide/show frame edges, show/hide selected frames, grids & guides, and story editor.

Literature review

In the era of the knowledge economy, magazines have a crucial role in the diffusion of knowledge. There exist a multitude of periodicals that encompass diverse facets of life. In September 2007, Mr. Wang Xiu compiled a list of 14 magazine categories for the National New Books Monthly, a publication of the National Library. The categories encompassed business management, social humanities, leisure and entertainment, natural sciences, children and youth, science and technology, finance and investment, language education, consumer lifestyle, arts and literature, health and medicine, internet and communications, news and information, and fashion trends. In addition, there are shopping guides, study assistance periodicals, and other such resources available.

Zhang Juming (1980) argued that magazines hold a significant role in the realm of mass communication. A magazine must primarily manage the tasks of text, image, and layout editing. Hence, it is imperative that we develop and meticulously strategize magazine editing principles and procedures. Yu Yelu (1986) primarily determines the effectiveness of a magazine's content through the design of its graphics and language. He regarded visual and text editing as analogous to orchestrating a symphony, necessitating flawless synchronization between language and graphics. Liu Minsheng (1982) emphasized the importance of achieving overall harmony and aesthetic impacts in the layout through the use of images and text in design. Magazines not only serve as a means of sharing information, but they also provide a visually appealing and atmospheric experience. Magazine graphic design utilizes shapes, colors, and lines to create captivating visual effects and provoke powerful emotions through meticulous design and skillful pairings. Wassily Kandinsky, the pioneer of abstract painting, held the belief

that the interaction between color and vision had the power to deeply impact and shape the soul. According to Wen Can, Jin Meizi, et al. (2011), colors are considered to elicit psychological perceptions in individuals. Sun Qi (1992) said that contemporary art places a strong emphasis on the underlying meaning of aesthetics, with aesthetics being the catalyst for evoking a pleasurable emotional state in individuals. Peng Jixiang (1994) asserted that the fundamental nature of art is its ability to offer spiritual gratification and elicit aesthetic experiences. Consequently, the impact of graphic editing in magazines on readers is significant. A photograph or a passage of words has the ability to have transformative force. Therefore, designers must carefully contemplate how to exert influence and stimulate liveliness through editing. Designers should also give this matter serious consideration. In her work, Catharine Fishel (2005) highlighted the significance of designing in a manner that deeply connects with people's emotions, thereby fostering a novel and invigorating environment for the design process. According to Debbie Millman (2007), the primary objective of an effective design strategy is to create an emotional connection with individuals. Hiebert Kenneth J. (1998) also believed that genuine works, infused with inner energy, have the power to evoke emotions and uncover significance, resulting in the production of valuable works. The editor's artistic approach revolves around enabling readers to grasp the essence of design, connect with it, and evoke a spiritual reaction. In his 2003 study, Nagumo Haruyoshi posited that the contour of an image and the amalgamation of hues have the ability to elicit diverse emotional states in viewers. Furthermore, comprehending these emotional states serves as a means of visually communicating with the audience. According to Wang Chuanghua (2000), line arrangement, light and dark contrast, and color application have the ability to generate diverse atmospheres and moods, as well as provide unforeseen outcomes for readers. Liu Siliang (1992) highlighted that lines, shapes, spaces, light, and colors have a significant impact on individuals' visual feelings and perceptions in the spiritual domain. Sensation and perception are the driving forces behind the examination of a work, ultimately resulting in a heightened level of interactive appreciation. In 2010, Kroeger, an expert in world design, instructed students to begin their learning process by examining the relationship between "lines" and "colors." Only after they had mastered this concept were they able to create visually striking and impactful designs. Lin Youchang (1987) emphasized that colors possess varying degrees of aesthetic attractiveness, can manifest distinct personalities, and can elicit symbolic connotations through association. Hence, magazine graphic design should integrate creative connotations to enhance its worth and optimize the importance of magazine graphic editing.

Methods

This study employs a research methodology that involves conceptual analysis within an informational analysis framework. This approach utilizes computer application software to study and analyze different areas of magazine graphic editing. The study specifically examines operational strategies for performing visual editing tasks, such as manipulating master pages, text, images, vectors, colors, lines, layouts, illustrations, text, and packaging. We use conceptual analysis to deconstruct the difficulties associated with magazine visual editing. The procedure entails examining and evaluating the elements of text, graphics, and magazine covers according to Mr. Wang Xiu's classification of 14 magazine types. The categories cover a wide array of subjects, such as corporate administration, social sciences, recreation and amusement, physical sciences, youth and children, scientific advancements, financial matters, language instruction, consumer habits, artistic expression, healthcare, internet and telecommunications, current affairs, and fashion fads.

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Practical operation analysis involves utilizing Adobe InDesign CS 5.5 (ID) for computer processes associated with graphic editing. This study primarily employs the software to classify operation techniques into three categories of significance: essential, suggested, and discretionary. We recommend measures that enhance functionality and aesthetics, yet they are not mandatory. The designer has the flexibility to carry out discretionary actions. Computer Operations. The study provides a comprehensive analysis of the precise procedures carried out within the Adobe InDesign software. The operations encompass the following: File operations encompass several tasks such as creating new files, opening existing files, putting objects, saving documents, setting up documents, accessing file information, and packing. Text editing entails inserting and formatting text, as well as using special characters and glyphs. It also includes the management of text frames. Image editing is the process of positioning and fine-tuning photos within the design.

Results

1. Master Page Editing and Operation Strategies

(1) Master Page Editing Concept

The design of a master page (also known as a master spread) allows for consistency in applied pages. In other words, the primary goal of master page design is to apply the same design to specific or all pages, akin to the application of PowerPoint slide masters. A master page can function by creating page numbers, headers, and various elements for the page layout, such as article titles, lines, icons, or page numbers. Master page design can create a page style, prevent readers from feeling bored by monotonous pages, and allow viewers to always see article titles on the page.

A magazine or book can design different master pages and apply them to different articles to give readers a fresh impression of the page templates. Making changes to a master page will affect all applied pages at the same time. For example, if you update the master page to adjust margins and add columns, all applied pages will be updated. To enter the "Pages" panel in ID operation, first open the "Window," where the master spread row is at the top and the page row is at the bottom. If the master page does not need to restrict a specific page, you can click and drag the mouse on the "[None]" icon in the upper-left corner of the page panel to free that page from the master page design. The left and right pages of the master control the left and right pages of the layout, respectively. For instance, the placement of an image on the left master page will result in its appearance on all left pages that utilize the master.

The top and bottom of the non-binding side, as well as the opposite side of the binding side, are suitable areas for designing master page elements. You can place color blocks, vector graphics, images, text, lines, or page numbers in these areas. During operation and setup, you must first pull out a text frame, then place the design elements inside. For master page settings, changes to a single page require holding down the Ctrl and Shift keys while clicking on the object. However, you can change colors on a single page, but you cannot change frames on a single page, as altering a frame will also alter the frames on other pages. To modify the text on a page that has already applied a master page, click on the downward-pointing triangle in the upper-right corner of the page and select "Ignore All Master Page Items" to allow editing on that single page. To completely separate a page from the master, first click on the downward-pointing triangle and select "Remove All Local Overrides," which will remove the master's control over that page. Click on the downward-pointing triangle and select "Remove All Local Overrides" to reapply the master layout on a separate page.

There are five methods to create multiple master pages: (1) Click on the downward-pointing triangle in the upper-right corner of the page and select "New Master." (2) Right-click

in the master spread row and select "New Master"; (3) To create a new page, use the "Create New Page" icon in the lower-right corner of the page panel. (4) In the page row, drag a page into the master spread row to create a new master with the same settings as that page. (5) Click on the downward-pointing triangle, select "New Master," and then choose to load based on an existing master before making any adjustments or modifications to create a new master.

To apply master pages to layout pages, there are three methods: (1) Hold the Ctrl key to select the left or right pages, then select the downward-pointing triangle option and click "Apply Master to Pages" to choose which master to apply and input the range of pages; (2) After selecting left or right pages, hold the Alt key and click on the desired master in the master spread row (e.g., select specific or all right pages on one side, then click on the right-hand master to apply to those selected pages; likewise for left pages); (3) Save completed master styles to directly apply to page layouts in new documents (e.g., in a new document, open the Pages panel, click the downward-pointing triangle, select "Load Master Pages," and choose "File" to load and apply a previously designed and saved master file).

On the master page, you must create page numbers. First, plan the area for page numbers, then pull out a text frame on the left or right master page. Place the cursor inside, go to the Text menu, and select "Insert Special Character" > "Markers" > "Current Page Number" to insert the "A" marker representing that master. If you set page numbers on a "B" master, it will display the "B" marker, and vice versa. Then select the alignment. After numbering one side of the master spread, copy it to the other. To format page numbers, go to the downward-pointing triangle menu and "Pagination & Section Options" to set: (1) Page Number Style; (2) Section Prefix (text before the number) by checking "Include Prefix When Numbering Pages." (3) Section Marker (text before the number); (4) Start Page Number by checking "Start On." If page numbers for both pages need to display on the same spread, hover the mouse over the edge of the left-hand page number text frame until the mouse becomes a double-arrow, then drag towards the right frame edge to combine them, separating the two number strings with a slash or decorative line.

(2) Operational Strategies

For the master page operation items, the strategy order lists four "required," one "recommended," and one "optional" strategy, for a total of six items as follows. Strategy: Item /Operation as follows.

1. Required: Create New Master/Page Layout Controls/New Master.
2. Required: Insert Page Numbers/Insert Special Character/Markers/Current Page Number.
3. Required: Edit Page Numbers/Layout/Pagination & Section Options.
4. Recommended: Insert Text, Images, Lines/Drag out Text Frame on Master/Place.
5. Required: Apply Master to Pages/Pages/Apply Master to Pages.
6. Optional: Delete Master/Select/Pages/Delete Master.

2. Text Editing and ID Operation Strategies

(1) Text Editing Concept

Line combinations make up the text. When text enters the eyes, visual nerves transmit it to the brain, which produces encoded meanings. However, text is not merely functional for conveying messages; it can also evoke different feelings in readers through various forms. Therefore, the style of the article content should match the typeface attributes.

The article's main message should guide the planning of a layout's proportion, distance, and white space between text and images. Formally, the spacing between words, lines, and

paragraphs should be visually appealing and simple to read. In terms of content, it should be simple but not complicated, concise but not long-winded. On the layout, paragraphs should be distinct with a smooth flow. Semantically, it should be coherent and ordered, sincere without affectation, elegant without vulgarity, and gentle without harshness. Enlightenment should provoke profound reflection and moderation. It is logical to discuss it from various perspectives and ensure that the commentary is rational, well-structured, and objective. Descriptively, it should skillfully use verbs, precise wording, clear meanings, and delve into details. In terms of appeal, it is valuable to leave deep impressions, motivate, and provoke thinking.

Language expression should consider breadth and depth, avoiding speculation, exaggeration, and personal attacks. Text categories include headlines, subheads, body text, author, and notes. The use of colors in text should prevent visual chaos due to excessive variety. Unless meticulously planned, carefully select background images or colors paired with text to avoid burdening vision during reading; otherwise, avoid using extensive background images to highlight large amounts of text.

While text design effects can provide a unique visual impression for the entire article, it's best to apply them sparingly, focusing primarily on key points in the body for greater impact. For magazine article text, including word meanings, phrases, parts of speech, tones, styles, sounds, puns, enlightenment, literary/vernacular language, vigor, etc., it should follow different format attributes according to various types, such as art, literature, education, entertainment, etc. Only then can it appeal to the sensibilities and tastes of different reader groups, motivating joyful acceptance and reading interest while achieving appropriate design objectives.

ID has 10 default Chinese fonts and 221 Latin fonts. Various fonts present different textual style attributes, such as rustic, oceanic, abstract, and other conceptual styles. Text layout on a page should consider visual reading fluency, complete article expression, and material pairing needs when designing typefaces, fonts, line spacing, character counts, text frames, paragraph indents, and column numbers. The "Layout Grid" text frame serves as an effective tool for planning text blocks on a layout, as it displays the accommodated character count, calculates the inputted quantity, and allows for the setting of columns, gutters, letter spacing, and leading without displaying grids in the output.

You can enhance readers' visual attention by using framed lines, network lines, underlines, backgrounds, emphasis marks, or sidebars for text with special significance. For example, the "emphasis mark" function highlights key text; after selecting and highlighting text, right-click to enter the "Emphasis Marks" panel with various small icons like circles, ovals, and triangles. This panel also has another "Emphasis Mark" option to set position, size, and scaling. Additionally, opening the "Glyphs" option in the Text menu displays 12 different categories, such as numbers, currency symbols, and so on, allowing for the selection of related glyphs from different font systems to combine or apply to text.

There are three methods to insert text into a layout: (1) Create a new document from the file; (2) Drag out a text frame on the layout to copy or paste; and (3) Click "New Document" on the welcome screen. There are four ways to insert text: First, insert all text at once by holding the Shift key (the mouse cursor shows a solid 90-degree "S") until finished, then releasing the left mouse button. Second, insert text into a text frame by holding Alt (the mouse cursor shows a 90-degree "S"), placing text sequentially in the frame until complete. Third, place in a text frame; if a red "+" appears in the bottom-right, it indicates unfinished text placement; click the red "+" to continue placing until it disappears. Fourth, place text on specific pages by first selecting the page range while holding Shift+Alt; content will only appear on those selected pages without auto-adding new ones. Inserted text frames have a right-pointing triangle in the top right; clicking it allows you to re-insert continuation text into another frame. Press Esc to

stop placement before completion; to resume, click the red "+" in the bottom-right of the frame. With multiple text frames, the View > Show Text Threads option displays blue lines connecting frame contents in order. ID has the ability to import Word files, but it does not preserve formatting elements like fonts and colors, only paragraph styles. Therefore, it's better to import plain text files into ID before applying text design and layout.

(2) Operational Strategies

The text operation requires 8 "required" items, 2 "recommended" items, and 10 "optional" items, for a total of 20 items, as illustrated below- No. Strategy: Item | Operation.

- .1. Required: Better to import plain text files | File/Place.
- .2. Optional: Insert all text at once, suitable for text-centric content | Open text file, hold Shift.
- .3. Optional: Insert into text frame, suitable for pages with text and images | Open text file, hold Alt.
- .4. Optional: Sequential text frame flow, suitable for diverse text/image frames | Open file, click "+" in bottom-right.
- .5. Optional: Insert special characters | Text/Insert Special Character.
- .6. Recommended: Line break, column break, paragraph break, frame break | Text/Insert Break Character.
- .7. Optional: Special symbols or glyphs | Text/Type/Glyphs.
- .8. Required: Change horizontal or vertical text direction | Text/Writing Direction.
- .9. Optional: Text flow along path or shape | Tools/Type on a Path Tool.
- .10. Optional: Text (frame, stroke) fill color and gradient | Select then use color swatches or gradient.
- .11. Required: Show text frame order | View/Show Text Threads.
- .12. Optional: Layout grid text frame | Open file, select Layout Grid.
- .13. Optional: Edit composite fonts | "Composite Font Editor" settings.
- .14. Optional: Set side notes | Text/Side Notes.
- .15. Required: Convert vertical numbers/symbols to horizontal | Right-click/Rotate Vertical Roman.
- .16. Required: Text paragraph alignment, indent, spacing, drop cap | Window/Type & Tables/Paragraph.
- .17. Required: Prevent unwanted leading/trailing symbols | Text/Keep Options.
- .18. Recommended: Use bullets and numbering for listed content | Paragraph/Bulleted & Numbered Lists.
- .19. Required: Create character styles | Character Styles/Style Settings.
- .20. Required: Apply character styles | Character Styles/Load Character Styles.

3. Image Editing and Operational Strategies

(1) Image Editing Concept

The clarity of an image can create an instant interaction with the reader. Therefore, the presentation of an image must emphasize visual quality, message significance, and inherent connotations. Readers can influence an image not only through color and content material, but also by evoking mood associations, motivating text reading, and provoking spiritual dialogue. An image can provide readers with emotional impressions, artistic appreciation, human enlightenment, scientific exploration, social reflection, potential inspiration, thoughtful space, triggered interests, event exploration, and value commentary. For example, a photo of a filial son carrying his mother wrapped in a cloth to Tainan Municipal Hospital sparked widespread social discussion and reflection, even spreading to dozens of countries, demonstrating the profound impact images can convey.

Consequently, when photographing, editing images and text, or selecting materials, one should consider the theme, connotations, and potential impacts presented in the imagery. The extent of an image's influence and the depth of human reflection it provokes determine its value. You can combine images in InDesign with various effects to enhance viewer appeal, but it's important to avoid excessive rendering as it could blur the focal message. Exclude unnecessary subjects from the frame during photography to clearly highlight the main content, enabling viewers to understand the editor's intended connotations.

Based on the content style, image production can create artistic, creative designs or impactful spreads. To create various frame shapes for image placement based on draft designs, select them from the File menu. When the shape and frame don't match, the Object > Fitting options can adjust accordingly. "Fit Content to Frame" will distort the image to the frame proportions; "Fit Content Proportionally" will cause white space if the image is smaller than the frame; "Center Content" will only show the center portion for disproportionate scaling; "Fit Frame to Content" resizes the frame to the image dimensions; "Fill Frame Proportionally" may crop parts of the image but provides the best fit within a fixed frame. Therefore, it's advisable to refine images in professional editing software according to sketches before placing them in InDesign, while also combining vector designs from Illustrator for versatile, creative imagery.

(2) Image Operational Strategies

For image operation items, there are 4 "Required", 1 "Recommended", and 6 "Optional" strategies, totaling 11 items. Image Operation Strategies as follows: No. Strategy: Item | Operation.

1. Required: Place PDF, AI, EPS, TIFF, PSD | File/Place.
2. Optional: Copy and Paste file | Edit/Copy/Paste.
3. Optional: Drag and Drop file | File/Drag and Drop.
4. Recommended: Use Bridge to place | Open Bridge panel.
5. Required: Adjust image and frame position | Select/Drag or set X,Y values in Control panel.
6. Optional: Adjust image and frame size | Drag handles; Transform or Scale panels.
7. Optional: Image and frame fitting settings | Object/Fitting/Select desired fit option.
8. Optional: Remove image background method | Object/Clipping Path/Options/Alpha
9. Required: Stacking order for images | Window/Layers/Move layer up or down.
10. Optional: Image masking function | Stroke frame/Paste Into/Set area.
11. Required: Check image link management | Window/Links/Relink.

4. The researcher employs vector graphic editing and ID operation strategies.

(1) Vector Graphic Editing Concept

You can draw vector graphics using 21 tools from the toolbar, 5 functions in the Pathfinder panel, and color coordination to create an infinite number of vector graphic shapes. We can divide the 21 vector drawing tools into 16 shape design tools and 5 shape transformation tools. The shape design tools include Direct Selection, Position, Pen, Add Anchor Point, Delete Anchor Point, Convert Direction Point, Pencil, Smooth, Erase, Line, Rectangle Frame, Ellipse Frame, Polygon Frame, Rectangle, Ellipse, and Polygon tools.

The shape transformation tools are rotate, scale, shear, scissors, and free transform. The five Pathfinder functions are: Unite, Minus Front, Intersect, Exclude Overlap, and Crop. For example, you can set anchor points and stroke styles when drawing lines, as well as fill colors from the swatches panel. Holding Shift allows 90°, 45°, and 180° rotation. The Free Transform tool can simply pull out control points and rotate them. Once you select the rectangle, ellipse, or polygon tools, you can directly drag out or size shapes by values, selecting colors from the

swatches panel. Holding Shift while dragging edges changes dimensions proportionally. Holding Alt while dragging edges causes the dimensions to scale from the center point. To set dimensions numerically or scale proportionally from the center point, hold Shift+Alt. For polygons, up/down arrow keys increase/decrease side counts, and left/right arrows adjust inner curvature. For shapes drawn with the rectangle, ellipse, polygon, line, pencil, or pen tools, after selection while holding Ctrl+Alt, the > or < keyboard shortcut can be used to scale up or down. After selecting an object, the mouse can adjust the shear angle, or you can enter numerical values. After designing an object shape, corner effects can modify its corner styling. Applying different corner effects between two different-sized rectangles can create hundreds of unique framed styles for placing documents or images.

(2) Operation Strategies

For vector graphic operation items, there are 1 "Required", 2 "Recommended", and 8 "Optional" strategies, totaling 11 items as follows: No. Strategy: Item | Operation.

1. Required: Create various vector graphic frames | Rectangle/Polygon/Ellipse etc.
2. Recommended: Create iconic vector graphic frames | Pencil/Line/Bezier Curve/Pen etc.
3. Optional: Create diagrams and contextual illustrations | Place graphics, lines, and text.
4. Optional: Organize and transform multiple vector shapes | Window/Object/Pathfinder.r
5. Optional: Outline from overlapping multiple shapes | Pathfinder/Unite.
6. Optional: Crop overlapping area of top object by bottom | Pathfinder/Minus Front.
7. Optional: Remove non-overlapping areas of multiple shapes | Pathfinder/Intersect.
8. Optional: Make overlapping areas transparent | Pathfinder/Exclude Overlap.
9. Optional: Crop area of bottom object by top | Pathfinder/Crop.
10. Optional: Select corner styling effect | Object/Corner Options/5 styles.
11. Recommended: Create corner framed styles | Corner Options/Pathfinder/Exclude Overlap.

5. The researcher specializes in text and graphic editing, along with operation strategies.

(1) Text and Graphic Editing Concept

Text and graphics are complementary. We can categorize them into six types based on various appeals, content, attributes, styles, and artistic aesthetics. 1) Visually-oriented graphics; (2) message-oriented text; (3) Equal graphics and text; (4) Graphics-prominent impressions; (5) Text-prominent explanations; and (6) Graphics across spreads. The interrelationship between text and graphics on a page includes position, space, distance, white space, lines, contrast, and correspondence. Achieving visual aesthetics and harmony prevents imbalances from causing visual oppression.

Text and graphic pairings should emphasize the congruence between the image's connotation and the vigor of the text's description. Text wrapped around graphics requires clear integration, with concise, concrete descriptions of the image. Six types of text and graphic cover expressions exist: (1) full-bleed image and text; (2) non-bleed image and text; (3) extracted picture and text; (4) vector graphic and text; (5) graphic image and text; (6) composite multimedia and text. Establishing different databases for text and graphic applications is possible. To open the Library panel, you can create databases from the Welcome Screen or the File > New > Library menu, name them, and save them.

Once opened, you can drag completed graphic or text elements from the layout into the library panel. Files in the library can have item names and text/image types set up to facilitate future use. When you place text or graphic attributes on a page, they stay unchanged, but you can

update any changes in the original library file by right-clicking. While you can directly store text in the InDesign library, you can only show graphics as shortcuts (stored in their original locations) when saving content.

(2) Operation Strategies

For text and graphic operation items, there are 2 "Required", 2 "Recommended", and 4 "Optional" strategies, totaling 8 items as shows as follows: No. Strategy: Item | Operation.

1. Optional: Text wrap around object contours | Text Wrap/Wrap Around Object Shape.
2. Optional: Text wrap in rectangular boundaries | Text Wrap/Wrap Around Bounding Box.
3. Required: Object below text | Text Wrap/No Text Wrap.
4. Optional: Leave spaces for inline objects | Text Wrap/Jump Object.
5. Optional: Wrap text inside object | Text Wrap/Invert.
6. Required: Move text below after object insertion | Text Wrap/Jump to Next Column.
7. Recommended: Set positional relationships between text and objects | Text. Wrap/Anchored Object Options
8. Recommended: Set anchors between text and objects | Window/Anchored Object.

Conclusion

This study focuses on the core ideas and efficient methods for attaining expertise in image editing and layout creation with Adobe InDesign CS5.5. This study provides comprehensive guidelines for producing visually compelling and thematically unified designs through an extensive examination of various editing techniques, including master page design, integration of text and images, employment of vector graphics, and coordination of colors. The findings underscore the importance of achieving a harmonious blend of visual appeal and functional clarity, guaranteeing that each visual element enhances the overall effectiveness of the publication's communication. The operational strategies described in this article serve as a valuable tool for designers seeking to enhance their workflow and achieve exceptional outcomes in their graphic projects. Designers of all skill levels, from beginners to experts, can use the study's systematic approach to improve their abilities in modifying text and images.

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